

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Responsible Research Assessment Guidance

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1. Introduction

At the University of Bath, we assess research in line with our [institutional principles of research assessment and management](#). To ensure a consistent approach, we have developed a package of guidance materials to support colleagues in applying these principles in practice.

What is research assessment?

Research assessment happens across universities every day. It informs decisions about recruitment, promotion, internal funding, awards, and recognition. We assess research to understand, manage, incentivise and recognise quality contributions. Assessment may focus on a single output, a portfolio of research, an individual, a department or centre, or even an entire institution.

Who ensures research is assessed responsibly?

Everyone involved in assessing research or researchers, shares responsibility for ensuring that assessment processes align with our institutional principles. This includes those who design assessment processes or undertake assessment themselves.

Who is this guidance for?

This guidance has been designed to support individuals in a range of roles. Below are some examples of how it can be used:

- if you are involved in assessing research or researchers (for example, as a member of a promotions panel), follow this guidance when carrying out assessments.
- if you are involved in supporting assessors by designing or supporting the assessment processes (for example in preparation for a recruitment panel), follow this guidance to ensure that your processes are in line with our commitment to responsible research assessment.
- if you are being assessed (for promotion or reward), use this guidance to understand what to expect.

This guidance forms part of a broader package of support. You can visit the [Responsible Research Assessment webpage](#) to access:

- the Responsible Research Assessment online training module – mandatory for frequent assessors but open to all members of the University
- information on how to get support from the Responsible Research Assessment Working Group
- Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)
- further reading on responsible research assessment

If you think there is anything missing or unclear within this guidance, please contact us at research-culture@bath.ac.uk.

2. Our principles of research assessment and management

Key points covered in this section:

- Our approach to research assessment is founded on six core principles.
- These principles build on international frameworks such as DORA, the Leiden Manifesto and CoARA.
- They ensure research assessment is robust, transparent, fair and inclusive.

At the University of Bath, research assessment is shaped by our institutional principles of research assessment and management.

These principles were updated in June 2025 and build on the [San Francisco Declaration of Research Assessment](#) (DORA), to which the University is a signatory, the [Leiden Manifesto](#), the [Metric Tide](#), and the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA). They respond to an international movement to make research assessment more robust, transparent, fair and inclusive. The six core principles are summarised below.

Research assessment at Bath is:

1. **Centred on expert judgement**, for which qualitative evaluation and peer review are central. Criteria and/or indicators used must be carefully chosen in light of the purpose of the assessment and context. Where meaningful and appropriate, quantitative indicators can be used to support assessment, inform judgements and challenge preconceptions, but not to replace expert judgement.
2. **Set in the broader environment**, with awareness of the possible consequences of research assessment methods on behaviour and culture and the potential for indicators to reflect or introduce bias. Everyone involved in research at Bath is expected to conform to the University's code of good practice in research integrity and assessors must also complete unconscious bias training.
3. **Supported by reliable data**, using metrics appropriately, responsibly and in context.
4. **Tailored**, recognising one size does not fit all. Assessment takes into account disciplinary differences and is appropriate to the scale and context of the activity being assessed.
5. **Transparent**, with assessment criteria and methods available to all and processes regularly reviewed.
6. **Inclusive**, recognising a broad range of outputs and impacts, as well as contributions to and careers in research.

You can read the full [institutional principles of research assessment and management](#) on the University of Bath website.

3. Designing assessment – what to consider

Key points covered in this section:

- Establish the purpose, level, and focus of each assessment at the outset.
- Apply transparent criteria and identify appropriate forms of evidence.
- Ensure diverse, trained panels and fair consideration of personal circumstances.

Assessment processes can present challenges for those serving on panels, for example being asked to make decisions based on insufficient evidence, or being provided with a metric without any context of what it indicates. Taking time to design an assessment process can go a long way in making sure we are assessing as robustly and as fairly as possible. Careful design ensures everyone has access to the best available evidence, presented in the right form, to ensure a robust and fair decision.

To support fair, high-quality, and proportionate assessment, consider the approaches outlined below. These take account of the differing contexts in which assessment occurs. It is important for all those involved in the assessment to:

1. Agree on the purpose and level of the assessment

Be clear about the purpose of assessment (WHY are we looking to assess -is it to monitor, showcase (show off), incentivise, or reward?) and the level of assessment (WHO are we assessing - an individual, a group/ entity, or a higher education institute)?

These choices should inform both the method of assessment and what evidence is considered reliable or appropriate. The use of metrics as proxies in some forms of assessment has more impact on the entity being evaluated and therefore carries more risk, as demonstrated in Table 1.

For example, using metric proxies for institutional-level assessments for the purpose of monitoring progress carries much less risk ('low' in Table 1) than their use in individual-level assessments for the purpose of informing reward ('high' in Table 1).

Table 1 – Risk of using metrics as proxies for different levels and purposes of assessment (adapted from International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group (2023). *The SCOPE Framework*. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>)

Purpose	Level			
	Country	HEI	Group/ entity	Individual
To understand	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
To show off	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
To monitor	Low	Medium	Medium	High
To benchmark	Medium	High	High	High
To incentivise	Medium	High	High	High
To reward	High	High	High	High

Agreeing on the purpose and level at the outset is key to making sure that we design an appropriate assessment process.

2. Define the focus of the assessment

Understanding WHAT the focus of the assessment is will help determine what evidence is useful. For individuals or entities, assessment could focus on:

- *research outputs*
- *research contribution*, including impact, enterprise and engagement
or
- *total contribution*, including research outputs, research contribution (impact, enterprise and engagement), teaching (if relevant to the contract), and citizenship.

Table 2 below provides some examples of different research assessment exercises, their focus, and types of evidence that might be considered in each case. These examples are not intended to be prescriptive, and assessors must design processes in a way that is tailored to their specific context.

Table 2: Examples of research assessment exercises, focus and associated evidence.

Examples reasons for assessment	Research output reward/ prize	Internal funding stage gate/ research prize/ sabbatical	Recruitment/ promotion/ probation/ global chairs/ career	Departmental/ Institute/ Centre review
What is likely to be assessed in this context?	Research output	Individual's contribution to research	Individual's total contribution	Entity's total contribution
What might be considered in assessment?	Assessment of research outputs Other contributions to research & innovation	Assessment of research outputs Other contributions to research & innovation Consider including citizenship in assessment	Assessment of research outputs Other contributions to research & innovation Consider including citizenship in assessment Education and student experience contributions (where relevant to contract)	Assessment of research outputs Other contributions to research & innovation Consider including citizenship in assessment Education and student experience contributions (where relevant to contract)

3. Set clear criteria

For any form of assessment to be responsible, fair, and transparent, it is important to have clear criteria that are understood by both assessors and those involved in the assessment.

Criteria should be:

- transparent to both assessors and to the individuals/ entities being assessed;

- relevant to the purpose and focus of assessment; and
- focussed on quality.

The criteria should be tailored to the type and purpose of assessment, so think carefully about what information is needed - and what is not - to make a reliable judgement.

4. Identify relevant and reliable evidence

Decide what quantitative and qualitative evidence best supports a robust assessment against the criteria.

Where the exercise includes an assessment of outputs, refer to the guidance on evidencing quality (Section 5) to see which evidence options are supported.

5. Design a suitable assessment process

Design processes that enable individuals or entities being assessed to bring forward relevant and reliable evidence against the criteria, in a format that the assessors can meaningfully review within the time available and considering their disciplinary expertise.

This ensures the person or entity being assessed can provide, and assessors can receive, the best possible evidence to inform a robust decision.

Consider how to avoid individuals submitting unreliable evidence (See Table 3 – Metrics to avoid in section 5).

6. Appoint a diverse and well-briefed panel

All research assessment should be conducted by a panel, not an individual. Panel members should complete unconscious bias and responsible research assessment training and have an opportunity to ask questions before assessment commences.

Wherever possible, panels should be diverse. However, this may place additional burden on minoritised groups (e.g. female colleagues in male-dominated fields). When inviting those panellists, make it clear that it is acceptable to decline, and think creatively about how to achieve diversity, for example considering asking colleagues from a range of career stages, other job families, other disciplines, or external organisations. See Section 9 for more guidance on assessment panels.

7. Consider personal context in individual assessments

Ensure individuals are given the opportunity, within the assessment process, to disclose any personal context or circumstances such as part-time working, career breaks, illness, disability, caring responsibilities.

These and other factors may impact an individual's capacity to contribute to research, teaching and/or citizenship and may not always be known to the assessor. While there

is no perfect solution to account for personal circumstances, it is recommended - in line with student assessment practice - that all individuals are *still expected to meet quality markers* consistent with their career stage.

Panels should, however, consider accommodating *reductions in quantity or rate* of contributions.

Focusing on quality of contribution over quantity in the assessment process will reduce the likelihood of discrimination based on protected characteristic or temporary vulnerabilities.

[Click here to download an **Assessment Design Checklist**](#) to help you clarify these points.

4. Assessing research outputs – untangling three facets of quality

Key points covered in this section:

Research outputs can be assessed against three core facets of quality:

- **Contribution:** the specific contribution that an individual made to the research.
- **Quality of content:** evaluation of the novelty, significance, rigour, ethic and integrity of the research.
- **Influence, impact, visibility and reach:** the impact or potential impact the research output had within its field and/or wider world.

A core criterion for the assessment of a research output is its quality. However, definitions of research quality are complex and often contested. This section untangles the concept of quality and proposes three core facets to consider when assessing research outputs.

1. Contribution

Assess the contribution that the individual made to the research output. Understanding their input is an important first step to understanding the merit that should be attributed to it. This is straightforward for single-author outputs but for multi-author outputs, everyone's contribution will need to be more carefully considered.

2. Quality of content

Evaluate the novelty, significance, and rigour of the research. Is the research design appropriate, ethical, and performed with integrity?

3. Impact, influence, visibility, and reach

Consider what impact or potential impact the research output had within its field and/or wider world.

Often, research metrics that imply visibility, impact or reach (such as number of citations) are used as quick proxies for quality of content. This is not a reliable proxy. Citations could be positive or negative (for example, contesting poor quality work).

Raw citation counts also vary widely between disciplines, meaning they are often not comparable between fields even within the same department.

It is important we clearly define what constitutes the 'best available evidence' when assessing each of the three facets of quality, and equally, to identify which types of evidence are unhelpful.

To learn more about the evidence that can and cannot be used to assess each of the three facets, see the Evidencing Quality section below.

5. Evidencing quality – what metrics can tell us and how to use them responsibly

Key points covered in this section:

- Use metrics and indicators responsibly, selecting the best available evidence and contextualising it appropriately.
- Avoid metrics that misrepresent quality.
- Use the tables to find out what evidence could support the assessment of each of the three facets of quality (contribution, quality of content, and influence/impact/visibility/reach).

As set out in our institutional [principles](#), responsible research assessment ensures quantitative indicators and metrics are chosen for their robustness and reliability. No indicator or metric is perfect so we must use the best available evidence and ensure that it is appropriately contextualised.

Both assessors and those being assessed need a common understanding of what metrics indicate, their limitations and which metrics or types of evidence are, and are not, considered valid for assessment at the University of Bath (as approved by Research and Knowledge Exchange Committee in September 2025, and Academic Staff Committee in November, 2025). This helps ensure that:

- individuals being assessed are informed on what is considered the ‘best possible evidence’ and so can make their case as effectively as possible.
- individuals can effectively identify the outputs that they would like to put forward for assessment (for example, if an assessment process requires them to nominate their top three outputs).
- assessors are not provided with evidence or metrics, listed as ‘avoid’, that they cannot consider, but can then be difficult to disregard.

There are metrics and indicators that should be avoided in research assessment (see Table 3), either because they are not reliable indicators and/or because better evidence options exist.

Table 3: Metrics to avoid (approved by RKEC and ASC)

Metrics to avoid	Limitations
Journal impact factor	Describes average reach and/or visibility of outputs within the journal, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact. The content of the output is much more important than the publication venue.
Journal-level citation metrics that are field-weighted e.g. SNIP, SJR, Article influence score.	Describes average reach and/or visibility of outputs within the journal, normalised by field, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact. The quality of the output is more important than the publication venue.
Output count	<p>Used in assessment, output counts can drive undesired behaviours (e.g., to publish larger quantities of lower quality work rather than smaller quantities of higher quality work).</p> <p>Output counts bias towards individuals with longer careers and traditional academic career paths. Output counts disadvantage individuals who have spent time in industry, taken time away from work for caring responsibilities or illness, part-time colleagues, and those earlier in their careers. Does not account for differences in publication norms between disciplines.</p>
H-index	Biased towards individuals with longer careers/ traditional academic career paths. Disadvantages individuals who have spent time in industry, taken time away from work for caring responsibilities or illness, part-time colleagues, and those earlier in their careers. Largely accumulates over time, creating age-related bias.
Author-level citation metrics	Largely accumulates over time, creating age-related bias.
Raw citation counts	Decontextualised citation data that is not field-weighted or by year will not give a meaningful picture of the reach of the output relative to others in similar fields/ years of publication. Citations may also be positive or negative, and do not always imply positive impact/ visibility in a field.
Ranking or reputation of affiliated organisation	The identity of an institution cannot reliably indicate the quality of all researchers within it. Many low-ranking universities have exceptional departments/ research teams within them, and vice versa. In addition, exceptional researchers make judgements on which institution to join based on a variety of factors, including family circumstances. As such, in line with approved CoARA commitments, we do not allow 'trickle down' of institutional status to researcher assessments.

The following three tables (see below) describe types of evidence that may be utilised to support assessments of each of the three facets of quality (contribution, quality of content, and influence/impact/visibility/reach).

This list is not exhaustive. Metrics and evidence should only be used for the specific facet of quality that the table describes.

A common example of metrics being used inappropriately is where a metric indicating visibility, impact, influence, or reach is used as a proxy for the quality of an output's content. This practice should be avoided.

Although these metrics and evidence types have their limitations, they represent examples of 'best available evidence' and have been approved by RKEC and ASC.

The tables categorise each evidence type as:

- **Central evidence:** This is in line with the first of our six core principles that states "research assessment [...] is based on expert judgement for which qualitative evaluation and peer review is central." Where the assessment requires an individual to submit a statement (for example, a cover letter or description of research contribution in a promotions case) as a central part of the process, this should always be supported by evidence. Where peer review is a central form of assessment, assessors may still wish to use other supporting evidence to challenge or support their assessments.
- **Supporting evidence:** Examples are provided of quantitative and qualitative information that might be considered in an assessment process to evidence claims or assessments of quality. The list is not exhaustive, and individuals may submit alternative evidence (except for items listed under 'avoid' in Table 3).

Contribution

Table 4: examples of types of evidence for 'contribution'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the individual's contribution.	The role that this person played in the construction of the research output.	For multi-author outputs, an individual's description of their contribution may not reflect the understanding of, or be 'agreed' by, all authors. Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.
Supporting	Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) statement https://credit.niso.org/	The role that this individual played in the construction of the output, but not necessarily the relative significance of contribution.	CRediT has its origins in Life Sciences and may not capture all roles played across different disciplines. For multi-author outputs, the CRediT statement may not be 'agreed' by all authors.
Supporting	Authorship position	The significance of the individual's contribution relative to other authors, but not an absolute reflection of the significance, nor the nature of the contribution.	The order in which authors are listed is different across disciplines. In some cases, lists are alphabetic, meaning they are meaningless for assessments of contribution.
Supporting	Percentage contribution	The individuals' self-reported perception of the significance of their contribution relative to other authors, but not an absolute reflection of the significance, nor the nature of the contribution.	This is a self-reported quantification of a contribution which might be more reliably described qualitatively. An individual's perception of their percentage contribution may not be 'agreed' by all authors. Where all authors are asked to estimate their percentage contribution, there is no mechanism to stop the total contributions exceeding 100%, meaning estimates may be unreliable.

Quality of content

Table 5: examples of types of evidence for 'quality of content'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the quality of the output's content. <i>This may consider the novelty, significance, and rigour as well as research design, integrity and ethics.</i>	An indication of the output's quality according to the individual.	Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.
Central	Provision of the output itself (for peer review)	An indication of the output's quality according to the individual assessor(s)	Consider that peer review can be subject to bias. Assessors should be sufficiently close to the discipline to deploy their expert judgement on the novelty, significance, and rigour of the output, to include appropriateness of research design, evidence of ethical conduct etc. Having a panel of assessors would help ensure any disciplinary bias or knowledge gaps are minimised in the assessment process.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Internal peer review scores	A quantitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an internal review process.	<p>Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.</p> <p>Internal peer review can be subject to particular biases as colleagues are reviewing each other's work. Different practices across faculties, School and departments, means that not all individuals will have access to scores from internal peer review processes.</p>
Supporting	Internal peer review comments	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an internal review process.	<p>Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.</p> <p>Internal peer review can be subject to particular biases as colleagues are reviewing each other's work. Different practices across faculties, School and departments, means that not all individuals will have comments or feedback on their work from internal peer review processes.</p>
Supporting	External peer review comments	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by expert peers in an external review process.	Consider that peer review can be subject to bias.
Supporting	Other reviews (e.g. book, event or exhibition review)	A qualitative indication of the quality of the output as assessed by reviewer(s).	It may be helpful to consider the expertise of the reviewer, where this is not part of a formal peer review process.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Prizes and awards	The output has received recognition.	It may be helpful to consider who has made the award and on what basis i.e. what were the assessment criteria? Consider the frequency and value of the prize/award.
Supporting	Rigour of a publisher's peer review process	The peer review process that an output has been through in order to be published.	Consider the peer review process from commissioning to completion, including the nature and number of reviewers, editorial oversight, and other evidence of rigour. The purpose of peer review in this context is to evaluate the output's quality and its suitability for publication in a particular outlet. There may be reasons that an output is deemed as high quality but not suitable for publication in a particular outlet.

Impact, influence, visibility, and reach

Table 6: examples of types of evidence for 'impact, influence, visibility, and reach'

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Central	Contextualised evidence statement of the reach, visibility, impact and/or influence of the output	The impact or influence that the output has had according to the individual.	Consider that contextualised evidence statements may disadvantage individuals who are not native speakers of English, who come from international academic contexts, or who are neurodivergent.
Supporting	Policy citations	The number of times a research output has been cited, and in which policy documents.	Consider the nature of the citations. Research may influence policy and decision making in indirect ways that are not always trackable via policy citations. Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'.
Supporting	Number of patents	Whether the research output has led to a commercial patent, or the patent has been cited in research.	It is possible to file a patent that is not used. Consider the impact of the patents.
Supporting	Field weighted/ normalised citations by year of publication such as FWCI	How the reach and/or visibility of the output measures in relation to the average reach and/or visibility for similar publications, but not the quality of its content, or the nature of citations (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	Field weighted citation metrics are only of use in fields where there are enough outputs and citations to provide a robust baseline metric. Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Citation metrics may not be an accurate indicator of reach for all fields, disciplines or output types. For some researchers, significant publications will not be on the most commonly used databases.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Citation metrics that are based on the use of percentiles (within the field) rather than averages	How the reach and/or visibility of the output measures in relation to the average reach and/or visibility for similar publications, but not the quality of its content, or the nature of citations (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	Citations can be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Citation metrics may not be an accurate indicator of reach for all fields, disciplines or output types. For some researchers, significant publications will not be on the most commonly used databases.
Supporting	Collaboration citation metrics (e.g. international co-authorship, national co-authorship, academic / corporate co-authorship)	Whether the individual has published with international/ national/ corporate peers, but not the quality of the output or its impact.	Data may not always be complete (dependent upon good affiliation practice by authors). International, national or corporate collaboration may be more or less appropriate depending on the nature and aims of the research. As with outputs counts, counting international collaborations risks focussing on volume rather than quality, and may drive undesired behaviours.
Supporting	Event / conference attendees	The reach and/or visibility of the output, but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Attendance to events or conference papers could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected attendance can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Repository views for open access outputs	The number of views an output has had but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Views are not an accurate measure of consumption or how many people have read the output. Views could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected number of views can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Views may be split across more than one platform if the item has been deposited more than once. Not all platforms record views and downloads to the same standards, so metrics may not be comparable unless using the COUNTER standard.
Supporting	Downloads for open access outputs	The number of times an output has been downloaded but not the quality of its content, its impact, or its reception.	Downloads is not an accurate measure of consumption or how many people have read the output. Downloads could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected number of downloads can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Downloads may be split across more than one platform if the item has been deposited more than once. Not all platforms record views and downloads to the same standards, so metrics may not be comparable unless using the COUNTER standard.
Supporting	Altmetric attention insight	The reach and/or visibility of an output but not the nature of the attention it received (+ve/-ve), or its impact.	This only captures attention from sources online tracked by Altmetrics. Attention could be biased by age, gender, or perceived 'status'. Expected attention can vary significantly according to discipline, field and language. Consider that a raw altmetric score tells little and the nature of the attention and the context is required to communicate the impact.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Whether the output is open access	The visibility and accessibility of the output but not the reach or impact.	Consider whether the output is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discoverable and accessible without embargo or conditions - suitably documented (if data, code etc.) to support reuse - under a license that supports reuse .
Supporting	Whether the output shows evidence of open research practices.	The visibility and accessibility of the associated data of the output but not the reach or impact. Whether the output and data have been made 'FAIR' (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible).	Consider whether there is evidence of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pre-registration - publication of methods, protocols, etc. - co-design or participatory research methods - deposit of supporting software, code etc - further open research as a result of the output It may be more or less appropriate or achievable to make research data FAIR according to the discipline, fields or methodology.

Use	Indicator	What does this reliably tell you?	Considerations
Supporting	Journal identity	The identity of the publisher, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact.	The University does not support using journal identity as an automatic indicator of quality. It can be an indicator of the most appropriate venue to reach the intended audience for a particular output. There are many reasons why a research output would be published in a journal outside of those 'top-ranked' within a discipline (e.g. interdisciplinarity). The quality and content of the output is more important than the publication venue. However, the University does encourage publication in non-predatory journals with robust peer review processes.
Supporting	Book publisher	The identity of the publisher, but not the reach and/or visibility of the specific output, the quality of the output, or its impact.	The size and prominence of the most appropriate publisher will vary significantly according to discipline, field, and language. The quality and content of the output is more important than the publication venue.

6. How to find and use meaningful metrics – support for individuals being assessed

The Library provides [training and support on finding and understanding meaningful metrics](#).

7. Practical examples of ways to assess research outputs responsibly

Key points from this section:

- Choose an assessment approach that matches the context and purpose.
- Read our practical examples about options for assessment to ensure fair and responsible evaluation

There are different ways to assess a research output or portfolio of outputs. Below are some practical examples.

These options are not exhaustive. Departments, teams, and individuals should consider the appropriateness of these options for their local context and develop alternatives where required.

Option A: Assess the research output (or multiple outputs if assessing a portfolio)

Individual's submission: The individual supplies a link to or attachment of their research outputs. When assessing a portfolio, the individual selects their top three to five research outputs to put forward. It is not expected or realistic for assessors to read all of an individual's outputs – particularly if the individual is later in their career.

Entity submission: The entity selects an appropriate number of outputs (for example, five to ten), depending on its size and the scale of assessment.

Review: Outputs are reviewed by a diverse panel with expertise appropriate to the subject area. Reviewers understand responsible research assessment (RRA) and avoid metrics listed in Table 3. They recognise that assessing the content of an output based on novelty, significance, rigour, and design is much more important than the publication venue.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers are in a similar field and will be capable understanding the quality (novelty, significance, and rigour) by reviewing the output themselves; and
- reviewers have time to thoroughly read the output.

- the aim is to understand the individual's capability through their selected outputs.

Less suitable if:

- reviewers are not expert in the field; or
- reviewers are time-poor; or
- there is a high volume of outputs or individuals to assess.
- you would like to formally consider reach, visibility, impact.
- for the assessment of entities - unless the entity is the only affiliation (e.g. some Institutes/ groups) it may be unclear how the entity contributed to or aligns with the output.

Notes: If the output(s) are multi-author, and CRediT taxonomy is not used, it might be difficult to assess the individual's contribution.

Option B: Assess an individual's/entity's statement of their research output(s)

Individual's submission: The individual provides a statement (approximately 200 words) to describe

- 1) their contribution to the output;
- 2) its quality (novelty, significance, rigour).
- 3) its reach, visibility and impact (if required by the assessor).

The statement should not use any of the metrics listed as 'Avoid' in Table 3. Individuals should reference the best possible evidence options from Tables 4-6. Where an individual's research portfolio is being assessed, the individual should develop a statement for each of their top three to five research outputs.

Entity submission: As above, but reviewers may consider asking for a single statement which captures the entities' contribution to the outputs, their quality, and reach, visibility, and impact for five to ten outputs.

Review: A diverse panel of reviewers, familiar with the subject area, should offer primary assessment of the *claims* of novelty, significance and rigour in the field. Reviewers understand RRA principles, avoid any of the metrics listed as 'Avoid' in Table 3 and recognise that assessing the individual's description of content is far more important than the publication venue.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers are in adjacent fields and capable of assessing the claims to quality. Where reach and/or visibility is also assessed, the reviewer sufficiently understands the disciplinary norms to judge significance.
- reviewers do not have the time or expertise to interpret the quality, significance or rigour based on a review of the output themselves.
- the process includes recruitment processes with a question about outputs on the application form.

Less suitable if:

- reviewers are distant from the subject matter.

Option C: Assess an individual's or entities description of their contribution to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge

Individual's submission: The individual completes the section of a narrative CV (e.g., [R4RI by UKRI](#)) that relates to their ability to generate new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge. The individual is instructed to avoid metrics listed in Table 3 and refer to best possible evidence options in Tables 4-6.

Entities submission: As per 'individual submission', but complete with a focus on evidence of their collective ability to generate new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge.

Reviewer: A diverse panel close to the subject area reviews and understands the assessment of quality provided.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers would prefer to assess a single statement that captures multiple outputs and contributions.
- the goal is to understand the candidate's broader research capabilities and assess outputs quality in the context of other contributions to quality research (e.g. impact, research projects etc)
- reviewers are in adjacent fields and capable of assessing the claims to quality.
- recruitment processes will include a question about research contributions on the application form.

Less suitable if:

- the process concerns international recruitment. There is some early evidence¹ to suggest that international markets are less familiar with the narrative CV format, and roles attract fewer international applications when a narrative CV is required.

These examples are not exhaustive and are not the only options for assessing research outputs. Teams and departments retain flexibility to design assessment processes that are appropriate to their context, provided they are in line with the University's principles of research assessment and the guidance outlined in this document.

¹ Adams E., Casci T., Padgett M, Lab for Academic Culture, University of Glasgow, Alfred J., Catalyst Editorial, 2021. *Narrative CVs* [Online]. University of Glasgow. Available from: https://www.gla.ac.uk/media/Media_1059370_smx.pdf [Accessed 19 November 2025]

8. A framework for writing and assessing statements

Key points covered in this section:

- Combine context and evidence in statements to show what was achieved and why it matters,
- Focus on individual contribution and significance, not just outputs or metrics.
- Use a consistent framework, such as the CARE model to help with assessment.

Candidate or applicant statements are often used in assessments. Whether via CVs, grant applications or interviews – individuals put forward examples of their contributions, describe the quality of their work, and explain its impact to make their case.

Statements can be particularly useful when the reviewers are not experts in the field, or do not have time to read the outputs themselves. They also help provide context for supporting data and evidence.

However, it is important to remember that context without evidence (whether qualitative or quantitative) could be just as meaningless as evidence without context. Statements can also be subject to bias. If not handled carefully, they could, for example, disadvantage colleagues with dyslexia, or those for whom English is a second language.

When reviewing written statements, assessors should focus on the content, not the tone or choice of words.

Think of statements as important mechanisms to contextualise evidence.

The CARE model (Context, Action, Result, Evidence) below provides a consistent way of supporting individuals and assessors to understand how they can present, and consistently assess, written statements for robustness.

Figure 1: The CARE model

Below are three examples of candidate statements. Only one applies the CARE model correctly.

Example 1: My work explores innovative approaches to reimagining patient triage, drawing on diverse and emerging data sources to inform the development of forward-thinking predictive models. It reflects a strong commitment to inclusive research practices, particularly in embedding meaningful public and patient involvement and engagement (PPIE).

The approach has gained traction within the field, contributing to wider conversations around data-driven healthcare and equitable access. It has been recognised through high citation rates, inclusion in policy discussions, and has attracted attention in other domains. Media coverage has further amplified its reach, leading to new opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Overall, the work is helping to shape future directions in health informatics and patient-centred care.

Example 2: I am first author on a paper “Incorporating Socioeconomic and environmental data into patient triage”, which was published in The Lancet Digital Health (JIFX). The paper has attracted 300 citations from 10 countries with 200k views and two collaboration requests.

Example 3: In health informatics, I observed that existing patient triage algorithms often overlooked social determinants of health, which significantly affect outcomes.

To address this, I led a study with BANES Trust integrating socioeconomic and environmental data into a predictive triage model. This was the first time local authority, patient, and longitudinal research data were combined in this way. I was responsible for funding attraction, model design, analysis, and led the write-up as first author.

A resulting paper was published in The Lancet Digital Health, achieving a Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) of 3.2—over three times the global average—demonstrating strong influence. It was cited as a ‘best-practice’ approach in a Department for Health Review and, following a BBC feature with 200,000 views, led to collaboration requests from two additional trusts to pilot the model.

Assessing the examples:

Example 1 demonstrates how statements that provide context without any evidence are difficult to assess robustly and often our gauge of them will depend on the writing style rather than the content.

Example 2 provides evidence without any context of what the individual did, why the work was significant, or the context in which it was carried out.

Example 3 combined evidence and context effectively so we have a clearer picture of the individual’s contribution, the work’s quality and its significance.

9. Guidance for organising, chairing, and taking part in assessment panels

Key points covered in this section:

- The importance of completing the required training and actively challenging conscious and unconscious bias.
- The role of the Chair and creating an environment where every panel member feels able to contribute and speak up about bias or unfair practice.

Unconscious bias

All panel members involved in research assessment must complete the University's mandatory [Unconscious Bias training](#), and the [Responsible Research Assessment training module](#).

It is good practice for the Chair to start the panel meeting by reminding colleagues to be mindful of bias, both conscious and unconscious. They should encourage panel members to recognise different experiences, perspectives and values equally, and to support each other and the principle of robust and fair decision-making by respectfully challenging bias whenever they observe it.

Briefing panels

Panels should be briefed ahead of time on the assessment process, understand the task and can ask questions or raise concerns. Again, it is good practice for the Chair to remind the panel members of the process, criteria, and responsible research assessment considerations at the start of any panel discussion. This helps set the tone and makes it easier for panel members to notice and speak up about any comments or behaviour that fall outside the agreed approach.

Speaking up

Every panel member should have an equal opportunity to contribute and share their assessment. Panels will often include colleagues of different levels of seniority or power dynamics so the Chair should be careful to make sure that everyone's voice is heard.

Panel members should be encouraged to speak up whenever something does not seem right – for example if bias is evident, there is a deviation from the agreed process or criteria, or if discussions become unbalanced.

The Chair can create this environment by reminding panel members at the beginning of the discussion that they are encouraged to contribute and to raise any concerns constructively.

10. Scenarios of responsible research assessment in practice

The following scenarios provide examples of assessment practices that do and do not comply with our principles for responsible research assessment.

Scenario 1: allocating prizes and awards.

Flo is assessing research outputs for an award for research excellence. One of the research outputs is from a field very far from their own and due to this, as well as time pressures, Flo resorts to finding the journal impact factor and number of citations to help them understand the quality of the paper.

Question: Is this approach consistent with our RRA principles?

No

- Expert judgement and peer review is central to the responsible assessment approach at Bath.
- Reliable and responsible metrics can be used to support, but never replace, expert judgement.
- Journal impact factors and raw citation counts are not considered a reliable metric for quality.
- In this instance, the following actions could have improved the assessment:
 - The assessment process could have asked individuals to outline their contribution, the quality of the content including novelty and robustness of design, and its impact, visibility and reach in the field. This would help assessors in adjacent fields to access contextual information that supports their expert judgement.
 - Ensuring a panel of assessors would help ensure that disciplinary biases or knowledge gaps are minimised in the assessment process.
 - In the absence of the above, Flo could have requested expert peer review from someone closer to the research area.

Scenario 2: assessing job applications

Ali advertised a Lecturer role. When creating the role in Stonefish, Ali used one of the four questions to ask applicants: “Please describe your best 3 research outputs. Explain the contribution you made to each output, the quality of the research and its design, and the visibility, reach, influence, or impact of these outputs.”

Question: Is this consistent with our RRA principles?

Yes

Ali has encouraged the candidate to present evidence against the three core facets of research quality for research outputs (1 - contribution, 2 - quality of content, and 3 - impact, influence, visibility and reach).

By asking the question explicitly in this way, Ali has ensured the panel have the best possible chance of accessing meaningful evidence to assess against the criteria.

The question focusses on the quality of the candidate’s outputs not the number of outputs.

Ali would need to include a maximum word count for this question to ensure that the shortlisting process is as manageable as possible.

Scenario 3: assessing job applications.

Chandrika advertised for a Lecturer role. When creating the role in Stonefish, Chandrika used one of the four questions to ask applicants: "Please describe your contribution to research and the generation of knowledge and list the 3 research outputs that you would like to put forward to be reviewed."

Question: Is this consistent with our RRA principles?

Yes - partially

Asking the candidate to nominate their top three research outputs focuses on quality over quantity and is more likely to reflect the research identity of the individual than randomly selecting outputs from their publication list to review.

But!

Clarity: 'Contributions to research' may not be universally understood. It might help to be transparent with the candidates what will be considered (e.g. outputs, research grants, innovation/ enterprise, impact, research supervision or otherwise).

Format: If Chandrika was expecting a large number of applications, it would be unrealistic for the panel to review 3 outputs per candidate. This question may be better placed further along the recruitment process when there is a smaller pool of shortlisted candidates. Proposing a word limit would also ensure assessment is manageable for assessors.

The question could be rephrased: "Please describe your contribution to research and the generation of knowledge (including X, Y, and Z) in 300 words. Please also list 3 research outputs that you would like to be reviewed by the panel if you are selected for interview. Please note they will not be reviewed at shortlisting, so consider whether you would also like to summarise any of these contributions in your 300 word statement. "

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